

GROWING ORGANS IN A NUTRIENT MEDIUM WITH CANCER CELLS

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Abstract: Currently, the concept of organ culture in the laboratory and bio-organs is gaining great importance in the field of medicine and biotechnology. This article analyzes the fundamentals of the technology of growing organ cells in a nutrient medium using cancer cells, its molecular mechanisms and practical applications. Cancer cells, with their rapid growth and development properties, offer new opportunities for creating organoid models. The article discusses the high-quality cultivation of bio-organs by modifying the nutrient medium of cells, signaling pathways, and controlling the plant environment in bioreactors. At the same time, the use of cancer cells in organoid models for drug testing and regenerative medicine is also discussed. The article summarizes modern scientific research and innovations in the field of bio-organoids, revealing future scientific and clinical opportunities.

Keywords: Bio-organs, organoids, cancer cells, culture medium, cell growth, regenerative medicine, molecular biology, bioreactor, nutrient modification, drug testing.

New advances in organ biology and regenerative medicine, especially the development of organoids and bio-organ technologies, allow the creation of various parts of the human body in the laboratory. In this process, cancer cells, with their rapid growth properties, are recognized as a unique tool for the creation of new models. The growth mechanisms of cancer cells in a nutrient medium allow us to simulate the specific properties of organs. This article reviews the basics, advantages and limitations of the technology for creating bio-organs from cancer cells.

The concept of bio-organs and organoids is the creation of an organism at the cellular and tissue level in the laboratory. Biological properties of organoids. The role of cancer cells in the creation of organoids.

Cancer cells have the ability to grow rapidly in culture media, and the control of the culture media and its ability to develop organoids is good. The following steps should be used to develop the technology for growing organs from cancer cells.

Stages of creating bio-organs from cancer cells.

Creating a bioreactor and nutrient medium.

Possibilities of molecular and genetic modification.

The practical application of bio-organs based on cancer cells can be used in drug testing because we do not have the opportunity to use human organs to test drugs, but if these bio-organoids are used, great progress will be made in the development of pharmacology and the clinic.

The introduction of bio-organoids in the field of regenerative medicine and transplantation will help to develop transplantation in the medical field and solve problems with donors.

Creating disease models, which will allow us to treat global diseases and test new methods for treating incurable diseases.

Problems and future prospects:

- Cancer cell risks and safety precautions.
- Scientific challenges for technology development.
- New directions and scientific research.

The concept of bio-organs opens up new possibilities for creating organoids by effectively utilizing the growth properties of cancer cells in a nutrient medium. This technology opens up great prospects in the field of regenerative medicine and drug testing. In the future, scientific research must be continued to ensure safety and quality.

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